

**AN INEQUALITY FOR THE DISTRIBUTION OF NUMBERS FREE
OF SMALL PRIME FACTORS**

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Abstract

Let $1 < z \leq x$ be arbitrary real numbers, and denote by $\Phi(x, z)$ the number of positive integers up to x whose prime divisors are all greater than z . In this note we prove the sharp inequality $\Phi(x, z) < x/\log z$ for all $1 < z \leq x$, improving upon the classical sieve bound $\Phi(x, z) \ll x/\log z$.

1. The Result

One of the fundamental problems in sieve theory is the estimation of

$$S(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}, z) = \#\{n \in \mathcal{A} : \gcd(n, P(z)) = 1\},$$

where $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ is a subset of positive integers, \mathcal{P} is a subset of primes, $z > 1$ is a positive real number, and

$$P(z) := \prod_{p \in \mathcal{P} \cap [1, z]} p.$$

When $\mathcal{A} = \mathbb{N} \cap [1, x]$ and \mathcal{P} is the set of all primes, where $x \geq z$ is a real number, the quantity $S(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}, z)$ yields the number of positive integers up to x whose prime divisors are all greater than z . Throughout this paper we shall denote this quantity by $\Phi(x, z)$, namely,

$$\Phi(x, z) = \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ p|n \Rightarrow p > z}} 1.$$

By the inclusion-exclusion principle we have the explicit formula

$$\Phi(x, z) = \sum_{d|P(z)} \mu(d) \left\lfloor \frac{x}{d} \right\rfloor,$$

where $\lfloor a \rfloor$ denotes the integer part of a for any $a \in \mathbb{R}$ and μ is the Möbius function. This is the starting point of the sieve of Eratosthenes. When z is fairly small in

comparison with x but tending to infinity, say $z = x^{o(1)}$, it is easy to see, by the fundamental lemma of either Brun's sieve [7, Theorem 2.5] or Selberg's sieve [7, Theorem 7.2], together with a classical theorem of Mertens [9, Theorem 429], that

$$\Phi(x, z) \sim x \prod_{p \leq z} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) \sim \frac{e^{-\gamma} x}{\log z}, \tag{1}$$

where $\gamma = 0.57721\dots$ is Euler's constant.

Around 70 years ago, Buchstab and de Bruijn studied the distribution of uncanceled elements in the sieve of Eratostenes. Setting $u := \log x / \log z$ so that $z = x^{1/u}$, Buchstab [3] showed that for any fixed $u > 1$,

$$\Phi(x, z) \sim x e^{\gamma} \omega(u) \prod_{p \leq z} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) \sim \frac{\omega(u) x}{\log z}$$

as $x \rightarrow \infty$, where $\omega: [1, \infty) \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ is the Buchstab function which is defined as the unique continuous solution to the delay differential equation

$$\frac{d}{du}(u\omega(u)) = \omega(u - 1), \quad u \geq 2,$$

subject to the initial condition $\omega(u) = 1/u$ for $1 \leq u \leq 2$. It is convenient to extend the definition of $\omega(u)$ by setting $\omega(u) := 0$ for $u < 1$. Comparing this result with (1) we see that the asymptotic behavior of $\Phi(x, z)$ is somewhat irregular. Maier [11] gave an interesting application of Buchstab's result to the distribution of primes in short intervals. Using the fact that $\omega(u) - e^{-\gamma}$ changes sign in every interval of length one, he showed that for any given $\lambda > 1$ one has

$$\begin{aligned} \limsup_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\pi(x + (\log x)^\lambda)}{(\log x)^{\lambda-1}} &> 1, \\ \liminf_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\pi(x + (\log x)^\lambda)}{(\log x)^{\lambda-1}} &< 1, \end{aligned}$$

where $\pi(x)$ is the prime counting function. Building on Buchstab's work, de Bruijn [1] showed, among other things, that $\omega(u) \rightarrow e^{-\gamma}$ as $u \rightarrow \infty$ and that

$$\Phi(x, z) = \mu_z(u) e^{\gamma} x \log z \prod_{p \leq z} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) + O(x \exp(-(\log z)^{3/5-\epsilon})) \tag{2}$$

for $x \geq z \geq 2$, where $\epsilon > 0$ is any given real number and

$$\mu_z(u) := \int_0^\infty \omega(u - v) z^{-v} dv.$$

In fact, $\omega(u)$ converges to $e^{-\gamma}$ quite rapidly, as one can see from the graph of $\omega(u)$ below generated by Mathematica.

Indeed, Buchstab [3] showed that

$$|\omega(u) - e^{-\gamma}| \leq \frac{\rho(u-1)}{u}$$

for all $u \geq 1$, where $\rho(u)$ is the Dickman-de Bruijn function which is defined to be the unique continuous solution to the delay differential equation

$$u\rho'(u) + \rho(u-1) = 0, \quad u > 1,$$

with the initial condition $\rho(u) = 1$ for $0 < u \leq 1$. Combined with an estimate of de Bruijn on $\rho(u)$ [2, Equ (1.8)] this shows that $|\omega(u) - e^{-\gamma}|$ is

$$\leq \exp \left(-u \left(\log u + \log \log u - 1 + \frac{\log \log u - 1}{\log u} + O \left(\left(\frac{\log \log u}{\log u} \right)^2 \right) \right) \right).$$

Finer results on the asymptotic behavior of $\Phi(x, z)$ have been found by Tenenbaum. The reader is referred to his book [14, Chapter III.6] for detailed discussions on this subject.

In the present note we are interested in upper bounds for $\Phi(x, z)$ that are applicable in wide ranges. For instance, a theorem of Hall on the distribution of the mean values of multiplicative functions [8] allows us to obtain upper bounds when z and x are sufficiently large. To state his result, let f denote a multiplicative

function such that $0 \leq f(n) \leq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, and define

$$\Theta(f, x) := \prod_{p \leq x} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{f(p^k)}{p^k}\right).$$

Hall [8] showed that

$$\frac{1}{x} \sum_{n \leq x} f(n) \leq e^\gamma \left(1 + O\left(\frac{\log \log x}{\log x}\right)\right) \Theta(f, x). \tag{3}$$

This result was later improved by Hildebrand [10], and Granville and Soundararajan [5, 6] have developed a method that connects the mean values of complex multiplicative functions taking values in the closed unit disk with the continuous solutions to certain integral equations. Taking f to be the characteristic function of the set of $n \in \mathbb{N}$ with $\gcd(n, P(z)) = 1$, we obtain at once from (3) that for any fixed $\epsilon > 0$,

$$\Phi(x, z) \leq e^\gamma x \left(1 + O\left(\frac{\log \log x}{\log x}\right)\right) \prod_{p \leq z} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) < (1 + \epsilon) \frac{x}{\log z}$$

for sufficiently large z . The object of this note is to establish the following theorem which shows that the above inequality, with the term ϵ discarded, holds uniformly for all $1 < z \leq x$.

Theorem. *For any $1 < z \leq x$ we have*

$$\Phi(x, z) < \frac{x}{\log z}. \tag{4}$$

Moreover, we have

$$\Phi(x, z) < \frac{x}{\log z} - \frac{x}{2 \log^2 z} \tag{5}$$

when $z \geq \max(3, \sqrt{x})$ and

$$\Phi(x, z) < \frac{2x}{3 \log z} \tag{6}$$

when $\max(2, x^{2/5}) \leq z \leq \sqrt{x}$.

Proof. The case $1 < z < 2$ is trivial, since

$$\Phi(x) \leq x < \frac{x}{\log 2} < \frac{x}{\log z}.$$

For $2 \leq z < 3$ we have

$$\Phi(x, z) \leq \frac{x+1}{2} < \frac{x}{\log 3} < \frac{x}{\log z}.$$

This proves (4) for $1 < z < 3$. To prove (6) for $2 \leq z < 3$, note that $x \geq 4$ and that

$$\Phi(x, z) \leq \frac{x+1}{2} < \frac{2x}{3 \log 3} < \frac{2x}{3 \log z}$$

when $x \geq 5$. Moreover,

$$\Phi(x, z) = 2 < \frac{2x}{3 \log 3} < \frac{2x}{3 \log z}$$

when $4 \leq x < 5$. Hence (6) holds for $2 \leq z < 3$.

From now on we shall suppose that $z \geq 3$. Put $y := x^{2/5}$. By the arithmetic large sieve [4, Corollary 9.9] we have

$$\Phi(x, z) \leq \frac{x+z^2}{S(z)},$$

where

$$S(z) := \sum_{n \leq z} \frac{\mu(n)^2}{\varphi(n)}$$

and φ is Euler's totient function. Montgomery and Vaughan [12, Lemma 7] showed that $S(z) \geq \log z + 1.07$ for all $z \geq 6$. Combining this with the precise values of $S(z)$ for $3 \leq z < 6$, we find that $S(z) \geq \log z + 0.89$ for all $z \geq 3$. Thus we have

$$\Phi(x, z) \leq \frac{x+z^2}{\log z + 0.89} < \frac{x}{\log z}$$

whenever $z^2 \log z < 0.89x$, which is easily seen to be true when $3 \leq z \leq y$. This proves (4) in the range $3 \leq z \leq y$.

Now we treat the case $z \geq \sqrt{x}$. By Theorem 1 and the associated Corollary 1 in [13] we have

$$\Phi(x, z) = 1 + \pi(x) - \pi(z) < 1 + \frac{x}{\log x} + \frac{3x}{2 \log^2 x} - \frac{z}{\log z}$$

whenever $x \geq 289$. We compute

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{x+z}{\log z} - \frac{x}{2 \log^2 z} \right) = \frac{(z \log z - x)(\log z - 1)}{z \log^3 z}.$$

This implies that as $z \in [3, x]$ varies, the quantity

$$\frac{x+z}{\log z} - \frac{x}{2 \log^2 z}$$

is minimized at $z = z_0$, where $z_0 \in [3, x]$ satisfies the equation $z_0 \log z_0 = x$. Hence

$$\frac{x+z}{\log z} - \frac{x}{2 \log^2 z} \geq z_0 + \frac{z_0}{2 \log z_0} > z_0 + \frac{z_0 \log z_0}{2 \log^2(z_0 \log z_0)}.$$

Now (5) will follow if we can show

$$1 + \frac{z_0 \log z_0}{\log(z_0 \log z_0)} + \frac{3z_0 \log z_0}{2 \log^2(z_0 \log z_0)} \leq z_0 + \frac{z_0 \log z_0}{2 \log^2(z_0 \log z_0)}.$$

Simple computation shows that this is equivalent to

$$(\log \log z_0 - 1) \log z_0 + \log^2 \log z_0 - \frac{\log^2(z_0 \log z_0)}{z_0} \geq 0,$$

which clearly holds if $\log \log z_0 \geq 1$ and $(\sqrt{z_0} - 1) \log \log z_0 \geq \log z_0$. Since $\sqrt{t} - 1 > \log t$ for all $t \geq e^e$, it suffices to have $z_0 \geq e^e$. Using $z_0 \log z_0 = x$ we see that this is indeed the case when $x \geq 289$. It follows that (5) holds when $x \geq 289$. For $x < 289$ we verify using Mathematica that

$$1 + \pi(n) - k < \frac{n}{\log p_{k+1}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2 \log p_{k+1}} \right)$$

holds for all integers $9 \leq n < 289$ and all $p_k \in [\sqrt{n}, n)$, where p_k is the k th prime. This implies that (5) holds for all $3 \leq x < 289$ and $z \geq \sqrt{x}$. We have thus proved (5) in the range $3 \leq z \leq \sqrt{x}$, and hence (4) in the same range.

It remains to consider the range $y \leq z \leq \sqrt{x}$, where we necessarily have $x \geq 9$. We first prove (4) in this range. We assume that $x \geq 1,024$ so that $\sqrt{x} \geq 32$. For $1,024 \leq x < 5,800$ we have $y \geq 16$ and $1/\log z > 0.230$. It follows by the inclusion-exclusion principle that

$$\Phi(x, z) < x \prod_{p \leq 11} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p} \right) + 16 < 0.208x + 16 < 0.230x < \frac{x}{\log z}$$

for all $1,024 \leq x < 5,800$. Suppose now that $x \geq 5,800$. Since $y^3 > x$, any positive integer $n \leq x$ with all of its prime divisors greater than z must have at most 2 prime divisors. Hence

$$\Phi(x, z) = 1 + \pi(x) - \pi(z) + \sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p \leq q \leq x/p} 1. \tag{7}$$

We have by [13, Theorem 1] that

$$\pi(x) < \frac{x}{\log x} + \frac{3x}{2 \log^2 x}$$

and

$$\sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p \leq q \leq x/p} 1 \leq \sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \pi \left(\frac{x}{p} \right) \leq \sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \left(\frac{x/p}{\log(x/p)} + \frac{3x/p}{2 \log^2(x/p)} \right).$$

Note that $1/(1-t) \leq 1+2t$ for all $t \in [0, 1/2]$. Thus we have

$$\sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{x/p}{\log(x/p)} \leq \frac{x}{\log x} \sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{1}{p} + \frac{2x}{\log^2 x} \sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{\log p}{p}. \tag{8}$$

From Theorem 5 and its corollary in [13] it follows that

$$\sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{1}{p} \leq \log \frac{\log \sqrt{x}}{\log y} + \frac{1}{\log^2 \sqrt{x}} + \frac{1}{2 \log^2 y} = \log \frac{5}{4} + \frac{57}{8 \log^2 x}.$$

By Theorem 6 and its corollary in [13] we find that

$$\sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{\log p}{p} \leq \log \sqrt{x} - \log y + \frac{1}{\log \sqrt{x}} + \frac{1}{2 \log y} = \frac{1}{10} \log x + \frac{13}{4 \log x}.$$

Inserting these estimates in (7) gives

$$\Phi(x, z) < 1 + \frac{6x}{5 \log x} + \frac{3x}{2 \log^2 x} + \frac{13x}{2 \log^3 x} + \left(\frac{x}{\log x} + \frac{6x}{\log^2 x} \right) \left(\log \frac{5}{4} + \frac{57}{8 \log^2 x} \right).$$

Therefore, (4) will follow if we can show

$$1 + \frac{3x}{2 \log^2 x} + \frac{13x}{2 \log^3 x} + \left(\frac{x}{\log x} + \frac{6x}{\log^2 x} \right) \left(\log \frac{5}{4} + \frac{57}{8 \log^2 x} \right) \leq \frac{4x}{5 \log x},$$

which is equivalent to

$$\frac{\log x}{x} + \frac{3}{2 \log x} + \frac{13}{2 \log^2 x} + \left(1 + \frac{6}{\log x} \right) \left(\log \frac{5}{4} + \frac{57}{8 \log^2 x} \right) \leq \frac{4}{5}.$$

Since the left side is a strictly decreasing function of $x \in [e, \infty)$, it is not hard to see by direct calculation that the inequality above holds for all $x \geq 5,800$. We have thus shown that (4) holds when $y \leq z \leq \sqrt{x}$ with $x \geq 1,024$. For $9 \leq x < 1,024$, we confirm using Mathematica that (4) always holds in the range $y \leq z \leq \sqrt{x}$, finishing the proof of (4).

The proof of (6) is similar but slightly more complicated. We assume first that $x \geq 137,550$ so that $x^{2/5} > 113.6$. Note that

$$\Phi(x, z) = 1 + \pi(x) + \pi(\sqrt{x}) - 2\pi(z) + \sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p < q \leq x/p} 1. \tag{9}$$

By Theorem 1 and its corollaries in [13] we obtain

$$\pi(x) + \pi(\sqrt{x}) < \frac{x}{\log x} + \frac{3x}{2 \log^2 x} + \frac{5\sqrt{x}}{2 \log x}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p < q \leq x/p} 1 &= \sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \left(\pi \left(\frac{x}{p} \right) - \pi(p) \right) \\ &\leq \sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \left(\frac{x/p}{\log(x/p)} + \frac{3x/p}{2 \log^2(x/p)} - \frac{p}{\log p} \right). \end{aligned}$$

From [13, Theorems 5,6] it follows that

$$\sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{1}{p} \leq \log \frac{\log \sqrt{x}}{\log z} + \frac{1}{2 \log^2 \sqrt{x}} + \frac{1}{2 \log^2 y} = \log \frac{\log \sqrt{x}}{\log z} + \frac{41}{8 \log^2 x}, \tag{10}$$

$$\sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{\log p}{p} \leq \log \frac{\sqrt{x}}{z} + \frac{1}{2 \log \sqrt{x}} + \frac{1}{2 \log y} = \log \frac{\sqrt{x}}{z} + \frac{9}{4 \log x}. \tag{11}$$

Inserting these inequalities in (8) we obtain

$$\sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{x/p}{\log(x/p)} \leq \frac{x}{\log x} \left(\log \frac{\log \sqrt{x}}{\log z} + \frac{41}{8 \log^2 x} \right) + \frac{2x}{\log^2 x} \left(\log \frac{\sqrt{x}}{z} + \frac{9}{4 \log x} \right).$$

For $z \in [y, \sqrt{x}]$, define

$$u(x, z) := \sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \left(\frac{3x/p}{2 \log^2(x/p)} - \frac{p}{\log p} \right).$$

We claim that $u(x, z) \leq 0$ for all $z \in [y, \sqrt{x}]$. To prove this, let

$$h(x, t) := 3x - \frac{2t^2(\log x - \log t)^2}{\log t}$$

for $t \in [y, \sqrt{x}]$. Then

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} h(x, t) = -\frac{2t((2 \log t - 1)(\log x - \log t) - 2 \log t)(\log x - \log t)}{\log^2 t} < 0$$

for all $t \in [y, \sqrt{x})$, since the inequalities $\log t > 1$ and $\log x - \log t \geq \log \sqrt{x} > 2$ imply that

$$(2 \log t - 1)(\log x - \log t) - 2 \log t > (\log \sqrt{x} - 2) \log t > 0.$$

Hence as a function of t , $h(x, t)$ is strictly decreasing on $[y, \sqrt{x}]$. Note that

$$\begin{aligned} h(x, y) &= 3x^{4/5} \left(x^{1/5} - \frac{3}{5} \log x \right) > 0, \\ h(x, \sqrt{x}) &= x(3 - \log x) < 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus there exists a unique $t_0 \in (y, \sqrt{x})$ such that $h(x, t) > 0$ for all $t \in [y, t_0)$ and $h(x, t) < 0$ for all $t \in (t_0, \sqrt{x}]$. This implies that as a function of z ,

$$u(x, z) = \sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{h(x, p)}{2p \log^2(x/p)}$$

is decreasing on $[y, t_0]$ and increasing on $[t_0, \sqrt{x}]$. It follows that

$$u(x, z) \leq \max\{u(x, y), u(x, \sqrt{x})\}$$

for all $z \in [y, \sqrt{x}]$. It is trivial that $u(x, \sqrt{x}) = 0$. Since $1/(1-t)^2 \leq 1+6t$ for all $t \in [0, 1/2]$, we have

$$\sum_{y < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{3x/p}{2 \log^2(x/p)} \leq \frac{3x}{2 \log^2 x} \sum_{y < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{1}{p} + \frac{9x}{\log^3 x} \sum_{y < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{\log p}{p}.$$

Combining this with (10) and (11) gives

$$\sum_{y < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{3x/p}{2 \log^2(x/p)} \leq \left(\frac{3}{2} \log \frac{5}{4} + \frac{9}{10}\right) \frac{x}{\log^2 x} + \frac{447x}{16 \log^4 x}. \tag{12}$$

Applying partial summation and appealing to Theorem 1 and the affiliated Corollary 2 in [13], we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{y < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{p}{\log p} &= \frac{\sqrt{x}}{\log \sqrt{x}} \pi(\sqrt{x}) - \frac{y}{\log y} \pi(y) - \int_y^{\sqrt{x}} \frac{\log t - 1}{\log^2 t} \pi(t) dt \\ &> \frac{\sqrt{x}}{\log \sqrt{x}} \left(\frac{\sqrt{x}}{\log \sqrt{x}} + \frac{\sqrt{x}}{2 \log^2 \sqrt{x}} \right) - \frac{5y^2}{4 \log^2 y} - \frac{5}{4} \int_y^{\sqrt{x}} \frac{t(\log t - 1)}{\log^3 t} dt. \end{aligned}$$

Integrating by parts we obtain

$$\int_y^{\sqrt{x}} \frac{t(\log t - 1)}{\log^3 t} dt = \int_y^{\sqrt{x}} \frac{t}{\log t} d\left(\frac{t}{\log t}\right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x}{\log^2 \sqrt{x}} - \frac{y^2}{\log^2 y} \right).$$

It follows that

$$\sum_{y < p \leq \sqrt{x}} \frac{p}{\log p} > \frac{3x}{2 \log^2 x} + \frac{4x}{\log^3 x} - \frac{125x^{4/5}}{32 \log^2 x} > \frac{1.45x}{\log^2 x},$$

since $0.05 \log x > 0.59$ and

$$\frac{0.05x}{\log^2 x} + \frac{4x}{\log^3 x} - \frac{125x^{4/5}}{32 \log^2 x} > \left(4.59x^{1/5} - \frac{125}{32} \log x \right) \frac{x^{4/5}}{\log^3 x} > 0$$

for all $x \geq 137,550$. Together with (12) this allows us to conclude that

$$u(x, y) < \left(\frac{3}{2} \log \frac{5}{4} - 1.45 + \frac{9}{10} + \frac{447}{16 \log^2 x} \right) \frac{x}{\log^2 x} < 0.$$

This proves our claim that $u(x, z) \leq 0$ for all $z \in [y, \sqrt{x}]$. Consequently, we obtain by collecting the estimates above and using (9) that

$$\Phi(x, z) < 1 + \frac{x}{\log x} + \frac{3x}{2 \log^2 x} + \frac{5\sqrt{x}}{2 \log x} + \frac{xf(x)}{\log x} - g(x, z),$$

where

$$f(x) := \log \frac{5}{4} + \frac{41}{8 \log^2 x} + \frac{2}{\log x} \left(\frac{1}{10} \log x + \frac{9}{4 \log x} \right) = \log \frac{5}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{77}{8 \log^2 x}$$

and

$$g(x, z) := \frac{x}{\log x} \log \frac{\log z}{\log y} + \frac{2x}{\log^2 x} \log \frac{z}{y}.$$

Observe that

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{2x}{3 \log z} + g(x, z) \right) = \frac{x}{3z \log^2 z} Q \left(\frac{\log z}{\log x} \right) > 0$$

for $z \in [y, \sqrt{x}]$, where $Q(t) := 6t^2 + 3t - 2$. Thus we have

$$\frac{2x}{3 \log z} + g(x, z) \geq \frac{2x}{3 \log y} = \frac{5x}{3 \log x}.$$

Therefore, (6) will follow if we can show

$$\frac{\log x}{x} + \frac{3}{2 \log x} + \frac{77}{8 \log^2 x} + \frac{5}{2\sqrt{x}} \leq \frac{7}{15} - \log \frac{5}{4}.$$

This holds for all $x \geq 137,550$. Finally, we verify using Mathematica that

$$1 + \pi(n) + \pi(\sqrt{n}) - 2k + \sum_{i=k+1}^{\pi(\sqrt{n})} \left(\pi \left(\frac{n}{p_i} \right) - i \right) < \frac{2n}{3 \log p_{k+1}}$$

holds for all integers $9 \leq n < 137,550$ and all $p_k \in [n^{2/5}, \sqrt{n}]$. Hence (6) holds in the range $x^{2/5} \leq z \leq \sqrt{x}$.

This completes the proof of our theorem. □

We remark that (4) is best possible in the sense that for any fixed $\epsilon > 0$, it is not true that $\Phi(x, z) < (1 - \epsilon)x/\log z$ holds uniformly in the entire range $1 < z \leq x$. But when $2 \leq z \leq \sqrt{x}$, we expect that a somewhat stronger result holds, as we have seen when $y \leq z \leq \sqrt{x}$. It is possible to modify the proof to obtain (6) for

all $\max(2, \sqrt[3]{x}) \leq z \leq \sqrt{x}$. Applying this and the large sieve to the inequality [14, Equation (III.6.17)]

$$\Phi(x, z) \leq \Phi(x, \sqrt[3]{x}) + \sum_{z < p \leq \sqrt[3]{x}} \Phi\left(\frac{x}{p}, p\right) + \frac{x}{[z]},$$

we may deduce that $\Phi(x, z) < 0.8x/\log z$ holds uniformly in the range $\max(2, \sqrt[3]{x}) \leq z \leq \sqrt{x}$. However, it is perhaps even true that the stronger inequality $\Phi(x, z) < 0.6x/\log z$ holds uniformly in the range $2 \leq z \leq \sqrt{x}$, and a proof of this may require careful application of sieves in certain explicit forms. By examining the final part of the proof, we see that $\Phi(x, z) < Cx/\log z$ holds in the range $y \leq z \leq \sqrt{x}$ when x is sufficiently large, where

$$C > \frac{12}{25} + \frac{2}{5} \log \frac{5}{4} = 0.56925\dots$$

is fixed but arbitrary. Furthermore, if M denotes the maximum value of $\omega(u)$ for $u \geq 2$, then de Bruijn's result (2) implies that for any fixed $\epsilon > 0$, we have

$$(1/2 - \epsilon) \frac{x}{\log z} < \Phi(x, z) < (M + \epsilon) \frac{x}{\log z}$$

for all sufficiently large $z \leq \sqrt{x}$. It is easy to see that

$$\omega(u) = \frac{\log(u-1) + 1}{u}$$

for all $u \in [2, 3]$. According to Mathematica, we should expect $M = 0.56713\dots$ attained by $\omega(u)$ at $u = 2.76322\dots$ (which is the solution to the equation $(u-1)\log(u-1) = 1$). It is perhaps true that for every $\epsilon > 0$, the inequality $\Phi(x, z) < (M + \epsilon)x/\log z$ holds in the range $2 \leq z \leq \sqrt{x}$ for all sufficiently large x depending on the choice of ϵ only.

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